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RESONATE
Resilient Forests for Society

Native hardwoods, the resilience of the forest sector?

As frondosas autóctonas, a resiliencia do sector forestal?

International symposium | Simposio internacional

February 28 to March 1, 2024

Lugo, Galicia, Spain

Native hardwoods, the resilience of the forest sector?

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Executive Summary

Hardwoods species are increasing in area across Europe and are considered more resilient than extensive conifers areas that are suffering of drought stress and bark beetles, among other threats, thus it is foreseen to be crucial that the industry is adapted to use more hardwoods in the future. It is therefore relevant to exchange information on innovations happening across Europe in that field, and to discuss whether the industry will be able to adapt to such changes. Under this context and in the framework of the regional 'Project for Valorising Harwoods in Galicia' and the European project 'RESONATE 'Resilient forest value chains – enhancing resilience through natural and socio-economic responses', the Galician Agency for Forest Industry organized the **Symposium 'Native hardwoods, the resilience of the forest sector'**, taking place in Lugo, Spain. The aim was to bring expertise from other areas in Europe with Galician stakeholders as target audience. Over 100 participants from 10 European countries represented a mix of actors (administration 35%, research and academia 12%, industry 43%) and covered the main scopes of activities relevant to the Galician forest-based sector: forest management and wood processing industries, i.e. sawmills, wood-based panel industry, and bioenergy. The symposium gathered 32 speakers, half of them coming from Germany, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Finland, Latvia, Sweden and Switzerland. The event consisted of 3 days with 6 thematic sessions, 3 parallel interactive workshops, 2 technical visits, and one roundtable.

Considering the discussions in relation to the identification of the main resilience challenges in the region, the possible solutions and the necessary resources, the following recommendations were highlighted:

- The availability of exhaustive transdisciplinary knowledge, which allows a rigorous consideration of the relevant social, technical, economic and political aspects involved, is an essential requirement to obtain the necessary improvements that a context marked by profound changes will require. The social component is particularly important in an environment characterized by a very fragmented ownership and ongoing demographic changes. At this respect, personal and societal factors are often as important as economic rationalities.
- This integration of knowledge should contribute to raise awareness between the main stakeholders (forest industry, researchers, policymakers and forest owners) about the new circumstances and possible solutions. Only through coordinated and ambitious actions, effective measures can be implemented to respond to the existing challenges.
- The market´s demand and technological development play a key role. The transition to a circular bioeconomy opens up new opportunities that require innovation from different perspectives (products, processes and markets). These new opportunities represent a key element that should be seized, as a driving force, to boost a more resilient and sustainable forest management.

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- An enhanced mobilisation of hardwood species was pointed out to be essential in the development towards a more resilient use of forest resources in the future. This will require some important adaptations in terms of standardization (hardwood species grading), technological development and accompanying measures (inclusion in the building design codes and promotion, for example).

As a result of the discussions the European Hardwoods Innovation Alliance (EHIA) was reactivated. EHIA is a community fostering knowledge sharing, innovation and policy advocacy about the hardwood value chains, from forests (sustainable forest management, wood supply, mobilisation of forest owners) to end-uses (construction, furniture, interior, bioplastics, textiles, paper, biorefinery, and other innovative materials). It was launched in 2016 with an EIP-Raw Materials commitment. EHIA is lead and managed by InnovaWood (IW), the main European network for research, innovation and education in the forest and wood sector. All presentations of the symposium were published in the '**European Hardwoods Innovation Alliance (EHIA)**' open repository on Zenodo, in order to collect public results on hardwoods research and innovation from members, partners and related European-funded projects.

This document includes the links to the recording and pdf of each presentation, as well as links with information about the speakers and their institutions. The full recording and agenda can be accessed from the links below.

Keywords

Resilience, policy, forest ecosystem, forest management, biodiversity, bioeconomy, value chains, stakeholder engagement

Resumo executivo

No marco do proxecto rexional "Proxecto para a valorización das madeiras frondosas en Galicia" e do proxecto europeo "RESONATE 'Cadeas de valor forestais resilientes: mellora da resiliencia a través de respostas naturais e socioeconómicas', a Axencia Galega da Industria Forestal (XERA) organizou o Simposio 'As frondosas autóctonas, a resiliencia do sector forestal?', que tivo lugar en Lugo, España, do 28 de febreiro ao 1 de marzo de 2024.

As frondosas están a aumentar en superficie en toda Europa e considéranse máis resilientes que as extensas zonas de coníferas que sofren estrés por seca e escaravellos da cortiza, entre outras ameazas, polo que se prevé que sexa crucial que a industria se adapte para usar máis madeira de frondosas no futuro. Polo tanto, é relevante intercambiar información sobre as innovacións que se producen en toda Europa nese campo e debater se a industria será capaz de adaptarse a tales cambios. Así, o obxectivo era achegar coñecementos doutras zonas de Europa coas partes interesadas gallegas como público obxectivo. Máis de 100 participantes de 10 países europeos representaron unha mestura de actores (administración 35 %, investigación e mundo académico 12 %, industria 43 %) e abarcaron os principais ámbitos de actividade relevantes para o sector forestal galego: xestión forestal e industrias de transformación da madeira, é dicir, serradoiros, industria de paneis a base de madeira e bioenerxía. O simposio reuniu 32 relatores, a metade deles procedentes de Alemaña, Austria, Bélxica, Dinamarca, Francia, Finlandia, Letonia, Suecia e Suíza. O evento constou de 3 días con 6 sesións temáticas, 3 obradoiros interactivos paralelos, 2 visitas técnicas e unha mesa redonda.

Tendo en conta os debates en relación coa identificación dos principais desafíos de resiliencia na rexión, as posibles solucións e os recursos necesarios, destacáronse as seguintes recomendacións:

- A dispoñibilidade dun coñecemento transdisciplinar exhaustivo, que permita unha consideración rigorosa dos aspectos sociais, técnicos, económicos e políticos relevantes implicados, é un requisito esencial para obter as melloras necesarias que requirirá un contexto marcado por cambios profundos. O compoñente social é particularmente importante nun ambiente caracterizado por unha propiedade moi fragmentada e cambios demográficos en curso. Neste sentido, os factores persoais e sociais adoitan ser tan importantes como as racionalidades económicas.
- Esta integración de coñecementos debería contribuír a concienciar ás principais partes interesadas (industria forestal, investigadores, responsables políticos e propietarios forestais) sobre as novas circunstancias e as posibles solucións. Só mediante accións coordinadas e ambiciosas pódense implementar medidas eficaces para responder aos desafíos existentes.

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- A demanda do mercado e o desenvolvemento tecnolóxico xogan un papel fundamental. A transición cara a unha bioeconomía circular abre novas oportunidades que requiren innovación desde diferentes perspectivas (produtos, procesos e mercados). Estas novas oportunidades representan un elemento clave que debe aproveitarse, como forza motriz, para impulsar unha xestión forestal máis resiliente e sostible.
- Sinalouse que unha maior mobilización das especies de madeira dura é esencial no desenvolvemento cara a un uso máis resiliente dos recursos forestais no futuro. Isto requirirá algunhas adaptacións importantes en termos de estandarización (clasificación das especies de frondosas), desenvolvemento tecnolóxico e medidas de acompañamento (inclusión nos códigos de deseño de edificios e promoción, por exemplo).

Como resultado dos debates, reactivouse a Alianza Europea para a Innovación en Madeira de Frondosas (EHIA). A EHIA é unha comunidade que fomenta o intercambio de coñecementos, a innovación e a defensa de políticas sobre as cadeas de valor da madeira de frondosas, desde os bosques (xestión forestal sostible, subministro de madeira, mobilización dos propietarios forestais) ata os usos finais (construción, mobles, interiores, bioplásticos, téxtiles, papel, biorrefinería e outros materiais innovadores). Lanzouse en 2016 cun compromiso do EIP-Raw Materials. A EHIA está dirixida e xestionada por InnovaWood (IW), a principal rede europea de investigación, innovación e educación no sector forestal e da madeira. Todas as presentacións do simposio publicáronse no repositorio aberto "[European Hardwoods Innovation Alliance \(EHIA\)](#)" en Zenodo, co fin de recoller resultados públicos sobre a investigación e a innovación en madeira de frondosas dos membros, socios e proxectos relacionados financiados con fondos europeos.

Este documento inclúe a ligazón á gravación e pdf de cada presentación, así como enlaces con información sobre os relatores e as súas institucións. Pódese acceder á gravación completa e á axenda desde as seguintes ligazóns.

Palabras clave

Resiliencia, políticas, ecosistema forestal, xestión forestal, biodiversidade, bioeconomía, cadea de valor, proceso participativo

1 Hardwoods in Galicia

1 Hardwoods in Galicia | As frondosas en Galicia

1.1 Hardwoods biotechnology |
Biotecnoloxía de frondosas

José Martel Muñoz-Cobos

Xunta de Galicia, Spain

1.2 Hardwoods silviculture.
Marteloscope | Silvicultura de
frondosas. Marteloscopio

Roque Rodríguez Soalleiro

University of Santiago de Compostela,
Spain

1.3 Technological project for Hardwoods
in Galicia | Proxecto Tecnolóxico
para frondosas en Galicia

Francisco Pedras Saavedra

Galician Agency for Forest Industry,
Xunta de Galicia, Spain

2 Hardwoods innovations in Europe

2 Hardwoods innovations in Europe | Innovacións de frondosas en Europa

2.1 European networks and hardwoods construction |
Redes europeas e construción con frondosas

Uwe Kies

InnovaWood, Belgium

2.2 Decarbonization and cascade use of hardwoods |
Descarbonización e uso en cadoiro das frondosas

Klaus Richter

Technical University of Munich, Germany

2.3 Valorization of hardwoods in Europe |
Valorización de frondosas en Europa

Andreas N. Kleinschmit von Lengefeld

Homo Silvestris Europae, France

2.4 Biorefineries with hardwoods | Biorrefinerías con frondosas

Klaus Richter

Technical University of Munich, Germany

2.5 Tannins and barrels | Taninos e barricas

Brígida Fernández de Simón Bermejo

Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Spain

3 Forest industry. Opportunities and challenges

3 Forest industry. Opportunities and challenges | Industria forestal. Oportunidades e desafíos

3.1 Construction with birch | Construcción con bidueiro

Pekka Ritvanen

Avantwood, Finland

3.2 Densification with hardwoods | Densificación con frondosas

Oliver Kläusler

Swiss Wood Solutions AG, Switzerland

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3.3 Birchwood plywood and bioproducts | Contrachapado e bioprodutos do abedul

Latvijas
Finieris

Michael Kern

Riga Wood GmbH, Latvia

3.4 Lignin production | Producción de lignina

RI
SE

Ewellyn Capanema

Research Institute of Sweden (RISE), Sweden / Suecia

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4 Resilience assessment

4 Resilience assessment

**4.1 Climate change and resilience. Decision support tools |
Cambio climático e resiliencia. Toma de decisions**

**4.2 Resilience ladder. Forest owners and social demands |
Escada de resiliencia. Donos forestais e exixencias
sociais**

Anne Toppinen

University of Helsinki, Finland

Jette Jacobsen

University of Copenhagen, Denmark

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4.3 Resilience Dashboard | Panel de indicadores de resiliencia

Alice Ludwig

University of Natural Resources BOKU,
Austria

4.4 Hierarchical multicriteria decision analysis | Análise xerárquico de decisión multicriterio

Janni Kunttu | Blasius Schmid

University of Helsinki, Finland |
University of Natural Resources BOKU,
Austria

4.5 Adaptation measures across the value chain | Medidas de adaptación a través da cadea de valor

Annechien Hoeben

University of Graz, Austria

XUNTA DE GALICIA

FORTRA (Trazabilidade forestal)
 É unha ferramenta dixital voluntaria e gratuita que a Xunta de Galicia pon á disposición das empresas forestais para, baseándose na tecnoloxía blockchain, dar trazabilidade aos produtos de madeira, rexistrando as operacións de transformación que se realizan dende o monte ata o mercado.

i Etiqueta QR ofrece ao consumidor información sobre a orixe do produto e o seu

XUNTA DE GALICIA
 CONSELLERÍA DE ECONOMÍA, INDUSTRIA E ENERXÍA

amtega

Presenta os produtos galegos baseados na madeira como:

- Produtos de proximidade
- Pegada de carbono negativa
- Fonte legal
- Xestionados de forma sustentable
- Libres de deforestación

SIMPOSIO INTERNACIONAL

As frondosas autóctonas:
 A resiliencia del sector forestal?

INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM

Native hardwoods:
 The resilience of the forest sector?

XUNTA DE GALICIA **RESONATE**
 Resilient Forests for Society

As frondosas autóctonas:
 A resiliencia do sector forestal?

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Native hardwoods:
 The resilience of the forest sector?

5 Digitalisation

5 Digitalization | Dixitalización

5.1 Administrative information in Galicia | Trámites administrativos

Jacobo Aboal Viñas

Galician Agency for Forest Industry,
Xunta de Galicia, Spain

5.2 NOTIFOR Wood mobilization | Mobilización de madeira

Noelia Méndez

Lugo-Madera, Spain

5.3 FORTRA Forest traceability | Trazabilidade forestal

Isabel Puentes

Galician Agency for Forest Industry,
Xunta de Galicia, Spain

5.4 SINERXIA Management | Gestión

Hugo Rodríguez

Ametlam, Spain

5.5 TRAZAMAD Transport Traceability | Trazabilidad de transporte

Carlos Iglesias

FINSA, Spain

6 Regional strategies for hardwoods

6 Regional strategies for hardwoods | Estratexias rexionais para frondosas

6.1 Evolution of the hardwoods market | Evolución do mercado de frondosas en Europa

Maria Kiefer-Polz

European Sawmill Organization EOS

6.2 Valorization of hardwoods in France | Proxectos de valorización de frondosas de pequena dimensión en Francia

Véronique Vela Rodriguez

Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty, France

6.3 Valorization of hardwoods in Belgium | Valorización e transformación local de frondosas en Valonia (Bélxica)

Vincent Defays

Filière Bois Wallonie, Belgium

6.4 Valorization of hardwoods in Navarre | Valorización de frondosas en Navarra

Fermín Olabe

Department of Rural Development and Environment of Navarre,
Spain

A low-angle photograph looking up at several tall, leafless trees against a clear, bright blue sky. The tree trunks and branches are dark and intricate, creating a complex web of lines. A semi-transparent white horizontal bar is positioned across the lower third of the image, containing the word "About" in a bold, black, sans-serif font.

About

7 About

Galician Agency for Forest Industry, Xunta de Galicia

The Galician Agency for Forest Industry (XERA) is a regional public agency. It aims at the promotion of economic activity associated with the forestry industry, with the improvement of the competitiveness and innovation of companies in the sector and with the coordination of research and technological centres linked to the forestry industry. The regional project for the sustainable valorisation of the hardwoods in Galicia includes eleven actions aimed at the use of small and low-quality forests, so that, through silvicultural operations, they become forests with high-quality wood.

InnovaWood asbl

InnovaWood is the main European network for research, innovation and education in the forest and wood sector. Its mission is to act as a bridge-builder, connecting the wood research innovation and education community and beyond, raising awareness, spreading knowledge and providing strategic orientations, as well as increasing the understanding of the special role that forestry and wood sector can play towards global challenges.

European Hardwoods Alliance (EHIA)

EHIA is a community fostering knowledge sharing, innovation and policy advocacy about the value chain of hardwoods, from forests (sustainable forest management, wood supply, mobilisation of forest owners) to end-uses (construction, furniture, interior, bioplastics, textiles, paper, biorefinery, and other innovative materials). It was launched in 2016 with an [EIP-Raw Materials commitment](#). EHIA is managed by InnovaWood on behalf of its members interested in hardwoods innovation. The Zenodo open repository collects presentations, reports and other results from actions of the EHIA members and related European-funded projects. It is also part of the [EU Open Research Repository](#).

Horizon 2020 project 'RESONATE'

Forest owners require greater guidance in adapting forest management to mitigate climate-induced changes. The EU-funded RESONATE project will help direct decision-making towards enhancing the resilience of forests and forest value chains in response to four resilience challenges. These challenges involve the changing suitability of tree species due to climate change, increased risks of forest disturbances, changing societal demand on forest products and ecosystem services, and a decline in biodiversity. Researchers will conduct an integrated resilience and vulnerability assessment to determine how past and current site factors and management influence forest system resilience in different forest types and management systems across Europe. In addition, foresight studies based on scenario analysis will be enhanced through engagement with stakeholders.

Sobre a organización

Axencia Galega da Industria Forestal, Xunta de Galicia

A Axencia Galega da Industria Forestal (XERA) é unha axencia pública autonómica. Ten como obxectivo o fomento da actividade económica asociada á industria forestal, a mellora da competitividade e a innovación das empresas do sector e a coordinación dos centros de investigación e tecnolóxicos vinculados á industria forestal. O proxecto autonómico para a valorización sostible das frondosas de Galicia inclúe once accións orientadas ao aproveitamento de masas de pequeno porte e baixa calidade, de forma que, mediante operacións silvícolas, se convertan en bosques con madeira de alta calidade.

InnovaWood asbl

InnovaWood é a principal rede europea de investigación, innovación e educación no sector forestal e da madeira. A súa misión é actuar como construtora de pontes, conectando a comunidade de investigación, innovación e educación sobre madeira e máis aló, sensibilizando, difundindo coñecemento e proporcionando orientacións estratéxicas, así como aumentando a comprensión do papel especial que o sector forestal e da madeira pode desempeñar fronte aos desafíos globais.

Alianza Europea da Madeira de Frondosas (EHIA)

A EHIA é unha comunidade que fomenta o intercambio de coñecementos, a innovación e a defensa de políticas sobre a cadea de valor das madeiras frondosas, desde os bosques (xestión forestal sostible, subministración de madeira, mobilización dos propietarios forestais) ata os usos finais (construción, mobles, interiores, bioplásticos, téxtiles, papel, biorrefinería e outros materiais innovadores). Lanzouse en 2016 cun compromiso do EIP-Materiais primas. A EHIA está xestionada por InnovaWood en nome dos seus membros interesados na innovación das madeiras frondosas. O repositorio aberto Zenodo recompila presentacións, informes e outros resultados das accións dos membros da EHIA e proxectos relacionados financiados con fondos europeos. Tamén forma parte do Repositorio de Investigación Aberto da UE.

Horizon 2020 proxecto 'RESONATE'

Os propietarios forestais requiren unha maior orientación para adaptar a xestión forestal co fin de mitigar os cambios inducidos polo clima. O proxecto RESONATE, financiado pola UE, axudará a orientar a toma de decisións cara á mellora da resiliencia dos bosques e das cadeas de valor forestais en resposta a catro desafíos de resiliencia. Estes desafíos inclúen a idoneidade cambiante das especies arbóreas debido ao cambio climático, o aumento dos riscos de perturbacións forestais, a demanda social cambiante de produtos forestais e servizos ecosistémicos e un declive da biodiversidade. Os investigadores realizarán unha avaliación integrada de resiliencia e vulnerabilidade para determinar como os factores do sitio e a xestión pasados e actuais inflúen na resiliencia do sistema forestal en diferentes tipos de bosques e sistemas de xestión en toda Europa. Ademais, os estudos de prospectiva baseados na análise de escenarios melloraránse mediante a participación das partes interesadas.

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